

PSYCHOLOGICAL AND PEDAGOGICAL ASPECTS OF SELF-MANAGEMENT AND MOTIVATION IN PEDAGOGY

Dzhumaboyeva E'zozkhon Mamadjhonovna

Andijan State Pedagogical institute

Senior Lecturer, Department of Pedagogy and Psychology

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15293725>

Abstract: This article examines the issues of self-management and motivation in pedagogy. The impact of developing self-management skills on students' personal and academic success in the educational process, the role of motivation in learning activities and its effective methods are analyzed. The study presents and presents a wide range of ideas and observations about the relationship between self-management and motivation, as well as pedagogical methods that help improve communication between teachers and students.

Keywords: pedagogy, self-management, motivation, educational methodology, learning activities, student motivation, personal development, educational effectiveness.

Introduction. In pedagogy, self-regulation and motivation play an important role in increasing the effectiveness of the educational process. The interaction between teachers and students, the development of self-awareness and intrinsic motivation are decisive factors in achieving success in the educational process.

In pedagogy, the relationship between self-regulation and motivation is one of the important factors in the educational process. Students' self-regulation and motivation directly affect not only their academic success, but also their social and emotional development. These two concepts help to understand the changing needs, interests and goals of students in the educational process. Through self-regulation, a student manages his/her own educational activities, time, resources and emotions, which increases his/her intrinsic motivation and expands his/her opportunities for success.

Motivation is the student's attitude to learning, desire to work, and internal drive to achieve goals. This process develops through the interaction of internal and external factors. Internal motivation, that is, the student's personal interests and goals, helps to develop self-management skills, because the student has the opportunity to independently manage his activities. External motivation, on the other hand, occurs through incentives, an assessment system, or external tools used by the teacher in the educational process. The role of the teacher in developing self-management and motivation in students is important. The teacher must understand the process of self-management and motivation and adapt his pedagogical approaches so that he can help students.

Effective communication by the teacher, the organization of an interesting and goal-oriented educational process, help to form internal motivation in students. Teaching students to independently manage their learning can be a guide for them to set their own goals and develop the necessary strategies to achieve them.

Also, developing self-control and motivation in students has a positive impact not only on their academic success, but also on their personal and social development. When a student develops self-control, he develops skills such as analyzing his own performance, learning from successes and mistakes, as well as managing stress and organizing his time effectively. All of

this helps to increase the student's overall well-being, strengthen his self-confidence and expand his opportunities for future success.

The article discusses the importance of developing self-management and motivation in the educational process, effective methods and pedagogical approaches. It also gives ideas on what pedagogical methods should be used to develop self-management and motivation in students.

To develop self-management, students need to develop the following skills:

- Effective time management;
- Setting goals and making a plan to achieve them;
- Managing stress and learning from their mistakes.

The components of self-management are:

Information Acquisition: The learner must quickly assimilate new knowledge and apply it in practice.

Planning and Goal Setting: One of the first steps for effective learners is to set clear and measurable goals for themselves.

Self-Evaluation: The learner must be able to evaluate their own results and analyze their strengths and weaknesses.

Well-developed self-management directly affects the social and academic success of the learner. Several studies show that students who have self-management skills:

- Maintain their motivation at a high level.
- Achieve effective results in the educational process.
- Learn new skills more easily.

Motivation, as the internal drive necessary for people to act and achieve their goals, plays a very important role in the educational process. It forms students' interest in work, self-confidence, desire to work and the desire to achieve success in education. The psychological and pedagogical aspects of motivation complement each other and increase the effectiveness of the educational process.

In psychology, motivation helps to understand how people act to satisfy their internal needs and interests. Motivation, from a psychological perspective, is formed under the influence of internal and external factors:

Intrinsic motivation is the student's interest in himself, his natural passion for the activity, and his enjoyment of learning. This form of motivation arises from personal satisfaction rather than from the student's interest in the learning materials and secondary incentives in working with them, such as grades. Students with high intrinsic motivation show more interest in learning activities and show better results.

Extrinsic motivation, on the other hand, is formed under the influence of external factors in the student, such as teacher incentives, grades, or values in society. This form of motivation encourages students to achieve goals through external incentives (such as rewards or punishments). However, extrinsic motivation may not have long-term effects compared to intrinsic motivation.

In pedagogy, motivation encourages students to actively participate in the learning process. The teacher plays an important role in developing motivation in students, because the teacher's pedagogical approach, teaching methods and communication strategies increase student motivation. Pedagogical aspects of motivation include: Teacher influence: The teacher's attitude towards students plays a decisive role in the formation of motivation. The

teacher can conduct interesting and goal-oriented lessons, motivate students, reward their achievements and give impetus to their development. Teachers should use pedagogical methods aimed at developing students' intrinsic motivation.

Individual approach: Each student has unique needs and motivations. An individual approach to pedagogy requires taking into account the student's personal interests, strengths, and weaknesses. A teacher can succeed in motivating students by organizing lessons that are tailored to their goals. **Interesting and unconventional teaching methods:** To increase motivation, it is important to maintain students' interest in the learning process. A teacher can increase students' motivation by using non-traditional methods such as interactive methods, games, problem-solving tasks, and group work. These methods ensure active participation of students and keep them interested in the lessons.

Knowledge development and personal goals: The teacher should help students set goals that will help them develop themselves. These goals increase students' intrinsic motivation and give them the impetus to achieve their own success. Identifying students' personal goals and directing them to achieve them in the educational process increases their enthusiasm for learning. **Positive attitude and encouragement:** In pedagogy, a positive attitude and encouragement towards students are among the main factors that increase motivation. Teachers increase motivation by rewarding students' successes, encouraging them, and helping them achieve their goals. This increases students' self-confidence and motivates them to achieve success in the educational process.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it should be said that in pedagogy, the psychological and pedagogical aspects of self-management and motivation are an important factor in increasing students' success in the educational process. Educators need to use various pedagogical methods to develop self-management and motivation in students, since these processes directly affect the personal and academic success of students.

Internal and external motivation play a key role in shaping the student's interest and aspirations. In pedagogy, the teacher's approach to students, effective communication, encouragement and individual approach increase motivation and improve the effectiveness of the educational process. Developing motivation in students changes their attitude to learning in a positive direction and creates the basis for their future success.

The activities of teachers are of great importance in the development of these processes. Teaching students effective self-management skills and encouraging them through various motivational approaches significantly increases the effectiveness of the educational process.

References:

1. Ziyodullayeva, G. (2012). "Self-regulation and motivation" pp. 324-356
2. Makhmudov, A. (2010). "Pedagogical psychology", pp. 98-123
3. Turakulov, A. (2016). "Self-regulation in pedagogy", pp. 345-376
4. Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (2000). The "What" and "Why" of Goal Pursuits: Human Needs and the Self-Determination of Behavior. *Psychological Inquiry*, 11(4), 227-268.
5. Zimmerman, B. J. (2002). Becoming a Self-Regulated Learner: An Overview. *Theory into Practice*, 41(2), 64-70.

6. Schunk, D. H., & Zimmerman, B. J. (2012). Motivation and Self-Regulated Learning: Theory, Research, and Applications. Taylor & Francis.
7. Bandura, A. (1997). Self-Efficacy: The Exercise of Control. W.H. Freeman and Company.
8. Vygotsky, L. S. (1978). Mind in Society: The Development of Higher Psychological Processes. Harvard University Press.